

COMMON PROBLEMS IN SECOND LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Abstract: This article explains the issues in education and provides fact-based explanations for each alternative.

Additionally, many issues also were released, some of which were caused by teachers, others by students, and some by the school's environment. Students face difficulties with their limited language, poor focus, lack of self-discipline, disinterest, and difficulty speaking. Lack of professional development, poor methodological knowledge, insufficient teacher training, and difficulty using language accurately are among the issues facing teachers today.

Key word: Language proficiency, communication abilities, motivation, contrastive approach, second foreign language, bilingual education technology, interference, teaching, English language, issues, solutions, and teaching techniques, disrupted environment, limited teaching resources, and use of native language.

Introduction

The desire among people to learn foreign languages is growing quickly in the current world. And it is clear that being able to communicate in another language is the most important requirement. The advancement of science and technology, coupled with societal transformations, has led to improvements in education as well. There are several issues that come up when teaching a second foreign language. The

fundamental issue comes from students' limited knowledge of the necessity of learning a second foreign language and, consequently, their lack of desire. Furthermore, students find it extremely difficult to study a second foreign language from both the native and the first foreign language perspectives due to the unavoidable issue of interference (negative influence). Finding instructional strategies and resources that address all of these issues is a challenging task for teachers. In the process, the teacher sets up an environment for the students to use their prior knowledge of the first foreign language they learned to the second language they are learning.

This enables the process of learning a second foreign language to be accelerated and intensified, increasing its effectiveness. Teaching foreign languages, particularly English, to young children is beneficial and acceptable with our educational system in certain parts of the world.

So what issues did educators have when it came to teaching English?

"DISTURBING CONDITIONS IN THE CLASSROOM" stands for the first issue. The most crucial factor in teaching and learning is the environment. Problems with the environment were the main challenge faced by English teachers. The disturbed attitude within the learning environment causes teachers to get distracted and has an impact on the learning of languages. Both teachers and students are unable to learn effectively in this environment.

Teaching the language requires a welcoming and comfortable atmosphere in the classroom.

"LACK OF TEACHING MATERIALS" is the second issue.

When teaching a foreign language, teaching materials are quite important. Resources play a major role in teaching anything, not just language. It becomes extremely challenging to teach without resources when teachers aren't given enough of them, particularly during lectures. Projectors, computers, and other digital gadgets are among the resources.

"A HUGE NUMBER OF STUDENTS IN THE CLASSROOM" becomes the third issue.

Due to the increased effort and hard work required to teach a large class, teachers deal with a lot of noise and stress from their students. In teaching, they are exhausted. They face challenges in managing the students in the class.

"LACK OF TIME FOR LESSON TO TEACH" is additional issues.

Time is the most vital thing in learning languages. The time of the class is very little for the teachers to teach English. It is one of the hardest tasks for the teachers to teach in less time. This is probably not possible for the teachers to complete the theme of their lectures in less time, that is not enough.

- The next problem in teaching foreign languages is that "USING OTHER LANGUAGES ESPECIALLY MOTHER TONGUE IN THE CLASSROOM".

Speaking in a native language in the classroom is the most noticeable problem faced by English teachers. For students, it is very effortless to speak in their native language which they can speak easily rather than the English language. It's very easy for them to communicate in their native language. This is a big issue faced by the English teachers in teaching language.

All other problems are of an applied nature and can be solved in practice. First of all, it is necessary to improve the material and technical base of teaching a second foreign language in order to introduce modern techniques and methods of teaching foreign languages. Then edit the curricula and study programs, increasing the amount of time-consuming credits, in no case sacrificing hours of other philological disciplines. It is necessary to plan the educational process in such a way that the load on the teacher is not excessively increased, but is comfortable with the appropriate level of remuneration for teachers, which should be as close as possible to the level of remuneration of the administration of the relevant institutions. Additionally, We can improve the quality of education by solving the problems we face in teaching English. Among other things, it is appropriate to mention the following methods as a solution to the problem

CONCLUSION

In summary, practice is the best way to master all knowledge. The exercise gives a positive outcomes not only in foreign language education, but also in gaining

knowledge in all fields. The activities of the pedagogue in the effective organization of the lesson and the role of modern pedagogical technologies is incomparable. Modern pedagogical information for effective organization of foreign language teaching process it is necessary to obtain knowledge of communication technologies. If pedagogues have a high level of general professional culture, social activity, independent thinking, ability to solve tasks without difficulty.

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